

The thrip attack was quite severe. The average damage score was 6. Of 390 varieties or lines. 21 were resistant, 49 moderately resistant, and 316 susceptible to highly susceptible. The resistant lines were also found moderately resistant to rice whorl maggot.

Cultivars found resistant to thrips were: B707C-MR-13-1 (Remadja//IR22/C₄-63G); IET 3817; IET 4506; IR5624-164-2-1 (IR841-85/IR2061//IR2049/IR2031); IR3264-30-2-3, IR7963-30-4-3, and IR7963-87-3-3

(IR3264-13/IR1702-74-3//IR2055-219-1); IR9129-2-2, IR9129-142-2, IR9129-169-3, and IR9129-393-2 (IR28/IR2053-521-1-1//IR2071-625-1); IR9218-2763 (IR36/IR2053-521-3//IR30); BW 78; MRC 505 (BPI-121-3-I/TKM6); IR2058-78-1-3-2-3 (IR1416-131/IR1364//IR1366/IR1539); CR 1016 (Waikoku/T 90); IR2798-88-3-2 (IR1529-680/IR1913-41//IR1514A-E666; TKM 6; Thirissa; IR4791-80 (IR3342/IR3341); and Kaohsiung Sen Yu 185 (IR1561-152-3/Kaohsiung 2). ■

Rice resistance to whitebacked planthopper

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A mass-screening method identified at AICRIP the cultivar IET6288 as highly resistant to the whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* Horvath, a major rice pest in northern and central India. IET-6288 is a progeny of the cross PTB18/PTB2//IR8.

To develop high yielding varieties with multiple resistance, IET6288 was

crossed with another high yielding variety, Phalguna, which is resistant to gall midge but susceptible to WBPH. Phalguna is a derivative of the cross IR8/Siam 29. The cross IET6288; Phalguna, designated as RP2149, was screened in the greenhouse. The F₁ plants were resistant to WBPH. The F₂ population had a ratio of 3 resistant to 1 susceptible. To confirm the findings, the F₂ population was screened three times in three separate lots. The same ratio was obtained in all cases (see table). The results show that in this cross, a pair of dominant genes control WHPH resistance. ■

Segregation for resistance to the whitebacked planthopper in the F₂ population of the cross IET6288 (resistant)/Phalguna (susceptible) (RP2149). Hyderabad, India.

Lot	Plants (no.)		X ² (3:1)	P value
	Resistant	Susceptible		
1	57	19	0.00	0.995-1.00
2	112	34	1.29	0.50-0.75
3	306	116	1.31	0.25-0.25
Total	475	169	0.51	0.25-0.50

Relative susceptibility of rice varieties to gall midge under low rainfall conditions

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The rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) has become a regular pest of the main-season (Jul-Nov) rice

1. Rainfall for 1979 and the average for 23 years in Bihar, India. Figures in parentheses are the number of rainy days during the month.

crop in Bihar, particularly in the Chhotanagpur plateau. Rainfall was deficient in 1979 (Fig. 1).

A field study was made of 19 rice cultivars, including two dryland and two rainfed wetland rices. Observations on silver shoot occurrence were recorded (50 hills/variety) in the second week of October — the infestation peak in 1979.

Among the dryland rices RAU40004-105 was most resistant (3.25% silver shoots) (see table). The two cultivars

Reaction of transplanted rice cultivars to gall midge in 1979 kharif, Ranchi, India.

Cultivar	Tillers (no./hill)	Silver shoots ^a (%)
BR10	13.1	0.2 a
BR34	14.2	3.1 b
RAU40004-105	6.6	3.3 bc
BR9	11.5	3.5 bcd
Panidhan	13.7	4.7 bcde
Pankaj	14.2	4.8 bcde
Archana	10.4	5.0 bcde
RAU40004-109	8.0	5.4 cde
RAU4009-3	6.8	6.1 def
IET2895	9.7	6.1 def
RAU4009-17	7.8	6.4 def
RAU4009-15	6.4	9.5 fg
IR26	12.6	12.5 g
BR8	11.1	13.4 g
IR20	12.8	14.2 g
IR30	9.0	15.3 g
Sita	13.5	21.5 h
Jaya	12.1	21.8 h
RAU4009-29	6.0	35.8 i

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

2. Rainfall and gall midge incidence. Ranchi, India.